

The effect of employee green involvement, green motivation, and green behavior on green business performance in textile companies in Indonesia

Muhammad Prastyo Susanto¹, Asep Rokhyadi Permana Saputra²,
Achmad Farid Firsalam³, Aminah Nur Rahmah⁴

¹PT Prima Sejati Sejahtera, Boyololi, Central Java, Indonesia

^{2,3,4}Management Program Study, Economics Faculty, Mercu Buana Yogyakarta University, Indonesia

Corresponding email: asep@mercubuana-yogya.ac.id

ABSTRACT

Green behavior is a behavior and effort to save the earth and the environment from the threat of damage. This effort is a concrete manifestation and responsibility that the company must also be aware of, as a positive contribution of the company and its employees to sustainable development. The concept of green behavior involves the involvement of environmentally friendly employees and environmentally friendly motivation to form environmentally friendly behavior to achieve environmentally friendly business performance. This research aims to analyze the influence of Employee Green Involvement, Green Motivation, and Green Behavior on Green Business Performance in the textile industry in Indonesia.

To achieve the objectives of this research, a research method was carried out using an inferential analysis approach, with a sample of 378 respondents using a random sampling method, cluster sampling technique, and sampling using Google Form. Questionnaires are measured using a 5-point likert scale. The analysis tool, inner model uses convergent and discriminant validity tests. Outer model with reliability tests using Cronbah's Alpha and Composite Reliability, and goodness-of-fit to see the fit of the model, all using structural equation models (SEM) with SmartPLS version 4.

The research results show that Employee Green Involvement has no effect on Green Business Performance, while Green Motivation and Green Behavior have a positive effect on Green Business Performance.

ARTICLE INFO

Received : Jan. 3, 2024

Revised : Jun. 3, 2024

Accepted : Jun. 28, 2024

KEYWORDS

Employee green involvement, Green behavior, Green business performance, Green motivation

Suggested Citation (APA Style 7th Edition):

Susanto, M. P., Saputra, A. R. P., Firsalam, A. F., & Rahmah, A. N. (2024). The effect of employee green involvement, green motivation, and green behavior on green business performance in textile companies in Indonesia. *International Research Journal of Science, Technology, Education, and Management*, 4(2), 35-49. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12730231>

INTRODUCTION

The phenomenon of global warming triggers an increase in ethical awareness about the environment, this encourages companies to apply the concept of "Go Green" in an effort to save the environment from the threat of damage. Currently of environmentally friendly is widely applied as a strategy, both of production, marketing, and the human resources. Environmentally friendly enterprise is a concept environmental protection and management in which corporate management, safety and health of stakeholders in all business decision-making. This is a concrete manifestation of responsibility and a desire to make a positive contribution to the company and its employees, especially to society and sustainable development (Manolas, 2017). To realize this, it is offset by the increasing number of textile companies that are implementing friendly to the environment.

Implementing the go green concept is not an easy problem, because green employee involvement is needed to achieve green business performance. The implementation of employee green involvement is an important supporting factor as a company step in making changes towards "greening" by providing opportunities for employees to be involved in implementing the environmentally friendly strategy set by the company. Lack of employee involvement causes low business turnover, decreased motivation, individualism, and environmental damage. This gap endangers the company in the medium and long term, therefore the more employees are involved in preventing environmental problems, the sooner they will be aware of the importance of protecting the environment (Dźwigoł et al., 2023), and directly assist companies in developing environmental management (Muntari et al., 2021). Furthermore, green involvement can actively help companies increase job satisfaction, work morale, and employee satisfaction to achieve productivity, this also helps companies in preventing company problems. (Purba & Tikurura, 2022).

To translate this application also needs to be supported by other factors, namely green motivation as a form of encouragement to employees to be more enthusiastic about implementing environmentally friendly (Y. Li et al., 2020) and supporting company success (Mittal, 2016). It is hoped that this involvement and motivation will lead to employee behavior that understands more about environmentally friendly strategies (Dumont et al., 2017), and in the short term will become sustainable green behavior at the organizational level (Özgül & Zehir, 2021). Green behavior is employee behavior that is conceptually voluntary (Cai et al., 2020) and positive as an intangible and enduring asset and a source of competitive advantage for the organization (Ahmed et al., 2021). When a company provides a work environment that cares about environmental interests, it will create a company that always promotes environmental values (Süßbauer & Schäfer, 2019). You can imagine that weak motivation will reduce team work performance, productivity, increase turnover, and if this becomes complete demotivation it will reduce company performance. These gaps will be eliminated in this research. It is hoped that this research can contribute to the development of science and can avoid negative impacts, and provide solutions, and be able to encourage company performance, therefore this research is important.

To facilitate this understanding, see Figure 1.

Figure 1. Research Framework

THEORY AND HYPOTHESIS DEVELOPMENT

Employee Green Involvement on Green Business Performance

Employee involvement will increase motivation by helping the organization, this will increase job satisfaction and enthusiasm for achieving productivity, and also help prevent organizational problems (Unsworth et al., 2021). The word “green” not only saves the environment, but also refers to the impact on living things on their health. (Uwem et al., 2021). Therefore, employees who have awareness share information and knowledge to increase environmental awareness and organizational health (Yuriev et al., 2018). Employee relationships are an intangible and enduring asset and a source of an organization's competitive advantage. This strategy was developed by the organization to be implemented with employee involvement (Rahman & Saputra, 2023), this determines the success of innovation, knowledge and ideas of employees involved in company activities (Q. Zhang et al., 2022). So it can be concluded that employee green involvement has a positive effect on green business performance, in full as in the first hypothesis:

H1: Employee green involvement has a positive and significant effect on green business performance.

Green Motivation on Green Business Performance

Green Motivation is an important factor in the green environmental performance sector because when employees are not motivated to comply with green practices, they will not be successful in implementing green practices, so business performance will decrease (Sun et al., 2022). With motivation, it makes them feel proud, happy, and excited about contributing to providing support for company employees (Nurhayati et al., 2023). When employees become motivated to welcome a green approach in organizational settings, the company gains a competitive market advantage (Malmendier & Wachter, 2021). Emphasis is very meaningful in seeing the dependence of the organization on employees, this is also reinforced by literature evidence which reveals that motivation can improve organizational environmental performance (Roscoe et al., 2019). In companies, green motivation is one of the critical activities that determines the success or failure of an organization's implementation which can improve business performance (Saepuddin & Saputra, 2023). Therefore, when employees are motivated because of green HR practices, it will ultimately result in a better environment (Soewarno et al., 2019). So it can be concluded that green motivation has a positive effect on green business performance, in full as in the second hypothesis:

H2: Green Motivation has a positive and significant effect on green business performance.

Green Behavior on Green Business Performance

Behavior is defined as a response to the environment, attitudes and personal characteristics, such as intrinsic motivation and personal norms that influence employee behavior, but still considering changes in behavior (Fawehinmi et al., 2020). This "greening" practice is an opportunity for employees to participate in the organization (Aggarwal & Agarwala, 2021). By planning and formulating environmental strategies that involve employees, it will encourage knowledge abilities to solve environmental problems directly and will also make a contribution (Venkatasatish & Dhanamjayulu, 2022). Environmental protection and environmentally friendly behavior are positive actions towards the conservation of company resources, and the evaluation of environmentally friendly behavior in the workplace (Sheikh et al., 2019). Therefore, it determines the impact of implementing environmentally friendly processes in companies, and is a key driver of sustainable societal and economic development (Soltaninezhad et al., 2021). Employee environmentally friendly behavior can reduce construction waste generation, thereby reducing company resource consumption (Jerónimo et al., 2020). Environmentally oriented forms of environmentally friendly behavior and the development of environmentally friendly products are beneficial in improving performance (Zhang et al., 2021). Based on this statement as in the third hypothesis:

H3: Green Behavior has a positive and significant effect on green business performance.

RESEARCH METHODS

This research model was adopted from Renwick et al., (2013), Green Motivation adopted from Ahmed et al., (2021), Green Behavior adopted from Cai et al., (2020), and Green Business Performance adopted from Yoestini et al., (2022).

Population and Sample

Population is a generalization of objects or subjects with certain qualities and characteristics determined by researchers to draw conclusions. (Hardani et al. 2020). 6,937 respondents is the total population, with slovin calculations and using $\alpha = 5\%$, a sample of 378 respondents is obtained. Slovin is used because the population is finite and in large numbers (Anokye, 2020).

Method of Collecting Data

The sampling method uses probability sampling with cluster sampling techniques. Cluster sampling is often used over large areas and is divided into homogeneous groups, making it easier to collect data. Data collection method using Google Form, which will be carried out February-May 2023.

Data analysis method

This research uses inferential statistics. Measurement with a 1-5 point Likert scale. The analytical tool is a validity test (inner model) with convergent validity > 0.70 (Chin, 1998), and Discriminant Validity with AVE > 0.50 (Hair et al., 2014), Reliability test (outer model) CA method and CR > 0.7 (Werts et al., 1974), and hypothesis testing, as well as goodness-of-fit (Bentler & Bonett, 1980), all using structural equation models (SEM) with SmartPLS version 4.

Variable Operational Definitions

Operational definitions of variables are needed to obtain information on how a variable should be assessed between research periods (Siyoto & Sodik, 2015). Details in Table 1.

Table 1. Variable Operations

Variable	Operational Definition	Indicators
Employee Green Involvement (Renwick et al., 2013) (Matthes & Wonneberger, 2014)	Employee green involvement is the application of HRM practices with the aim of promoting the use of sustainable resources, which prioritizes preservation.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Vision of environmental management 2. Green behavior and awareness 3. Communication of green culture in the company 4. Involvement on green issues 5. Employee participation in environmental management
Green Motivation (Mittal, 2016) (Ahmed et al., 2021)	Motivation is important for green environmental performance because if it is not motivated, then no one can implement an environmentally friendly plan successfully.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Motivation to finish the job 2. Motivate employees to carry out greening ideas 3. Employee involvement in the development of greening ideas 4. Recognition of employee greening performance 5. Appreciation for employee greening

		performance
		6. Compensation for employee environmental duties
Green Behavior (Boiral & Paillé, 2012) (Cai et al., 2020)	Green behavior is the behavior of protecting and caring for the environment which is carried out because of awareness and a sense of responsibility for the preservation of the universe.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Behavior of employees' understanding of the concept of environmentally friendly 2. Employees responsibility for implementing environmentally friendly concepts 3. Obedience to the leadership regarding the concept of environmentally friendly 4. Employee involvement in greening activities 5. Employee initiatives to act environmentally friendly
Green Business Performance (Liu et al., 2021) (Yoestini et al., 2022)	Green business performance is the efforts made by the company to minimize the negative impacts of the company's economic activities on the local and global community, society, economy and environment by fulfilling the principles of the triple bottom line of business.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Higher development compared to competitors 2. Higher growth compared to competitors 3. Adequate operating income 4. Higher market dominance

RESULT

Respondent Descriptive Analysis

Table 2. Respondents' Descriptive Analysis

Indicators	Amount	Percentage (%)
Company group		
PT Prima Sejati Sejahtera (PSS)	162	42,9
PT PSS 1	115	30,4
PT PSS 2	101	26,7
Gender		
Man	114	30,2
Woman	264	69,8
Age		
<20	92	24,3
20-30	164	43,4
30-50	68	18,0
>50	54	14,3
Marital Statues		
Not married yet	108	28,6
Merried	270	71,4
Level of education		

Senior High School	182	48,1
Diploma 2 (D2)	90	23,8
Diploma 3 (D3)	72	19,1
Bachelor degree	30	7,9
Postgraduate	4	1,1
Employee status		
Contract employees	94	24,9
Permanent employees	284	75,1
Sub Division		
Production	348	92,1
Maintenance	24	6,3
Administration & Quality Control	6	1,6
Length of service		
<5	89	23,6
5-10	104	27,5
10-25	118	31,2
>25	67	17,7

Based on Table 2, the sample of respondents was dominated by PT Prima Sejati Sejahtera 42.9%, female sex 69.8% aged 20-30 years 43.4% married status 71.4%. Education, dominated at the SMA/SMK level 48.1%. Employment status as permanent employees 75.1%. the sub division is dominated by production with 92.1% with 10-25 years of service 31.2%.

Means and Outer Loading

Table 3. Means and Outer Loading

Variable	Questionnaire	Mean	Loading
<i>Green Business Performance</i> (Y)	Y1.1 The development of our company is higher than that of our main competitors	3,83**	0,848
	Y1.2 The growth of our company is higher than that of our main competitors	3,79	0,865
	Y1.3 Our company has sufficient operating income for the coming years	3,56*	0,792
	Y1.4 Our company dominates the higher market	3,78	0,857
<i>Employee Green Involvement</i> (X1)	X1.1 The company vision is clear in guiding environmental management for employees	3,85	0,793
	X1.2 The process of mutual learning fosters environmentally friendly awareness among employees in the company	3,87**	0,854

	X1.3	Green Culture has become an informal and formal communication in our company	3,66*	0,833
	X1.4	Environmental problems are solved by involving employees to improve quality	3,77	0,855
	X1.5	There are practices for employees in environmental management participation, for example group schemes, low carbon applications, and green response teams	3,70	0,854
<i>Green Motivation (X2)</i>	X2.1	I enjoy trying to complete environmental assignments at work	3,75*	0,818
	X2.2	I like to implement ideas related to greening in my work	3,84	0,764
	X2.3	I feel like I'm becoming more involved in developing greening ideas	3,79	0,841
	X2.4	The environmental tasks that motivate me the most are recognized by the company.	3,87**	0,728
	X2.5	Task environment drives rewards, promotions and pay.	3,84	0,855
	X2.6	I feel that I am being rewarded for my environmental duties	3,78	0,829
<i>Green Behavior (X3)</i>	X3.1	Environmentally friendly office tasks are completed, but always pay attention to and implement the concept..	4,02	0,793
	X3.2	The concept of being environmentally friendly is my responsibility at the office.	4,12**	0,851
	X3.3	Environmentally friendly concepts are still implemented even though it is the task of the leadership.	3,94	0,846
	X3.4	Environmental protection activities in my office play an active role.	3,73*	0,851
	X3.5	Environmentally friendly habits as an initiative to reduce paper waste, save electricity and cleanliness, as well as other resources.	3,93	0,735

* *Lowest mean*

** *Highest mean*

Table 3 shows that all variable indicators are valid and therefore > 0.7.

Average Variance Extrancted (AVE), Cronbach's Alpha (CA), and Composite Reliability (CR) Test

Table 4 shows that convergent validity is fulfilled because the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) value is > 0.50, so it is said to be valid, meanwhile the variable construct is also completely reliable because in the collom 3 and 4 are > 0.70 (Sarstedt et al., 2014).

Table 4. AVE, CA, and CR Test

Variable	AVE	CA	CR	Result
<i>Employee Green Involvement (X1)</i>	0,702	0,894	0,922	<i>Valid and reliable</i>
<i>Green Motivation (X2)</i>	0,651	0,892	0,918	<i>Valid and reliable</i>
<i>Green Behavior (X3)</i>	0,667	0,874	0,909	<i>Valid and reliable</i>
<i>Green Business Performance (Y)</i>	0,708	0,863	0,906	<i>Valid and reliable</i>

Table 4, the four variables and 20 measurement indicators, there are high consistency. Discriminant Validity

Table 5. Discriminant Validity (Fornell Larcker C)

Variable	<i>Employee Green Involvement (X1)</i>	<i>Green Motivation (X2)</i>	<i>Green Behavior (X3)</i>	<i>Green Business Performance (Y)</i>
<i>Employee Green Involvement (X1)</i>	0,838			
<i>Green Motivation (X2)</i>	0,838	0,807		
<i>Green Behavior (X3)</i>	0,776	0,877	0,817	
<i>Green Business Performance (Y)</i>	0,717	0,860	0,807	0,841

Estimated discriminant construct, square root of AVE, construct > compared to the correlation of the two model constructs (Fornell & Larcker, 1981).

Goodness of Fit (GoF)

Table 6. Goodness of Fit

Indicators	Result	Criteria
SRMR	0.073	<i>acceptable if <= 0.08</i>
d_ ULS	1.444	<i>acceptable if >= 0.95</i>
d_ G	1.016	<i>acceptable if P >= 0.05</i>
Chi-square	172.674	<i>close to zero</i>
NFI	0.929	<i>acceptable if >= 0.90</i>

Evaluate the suitability between the observed correlations using SMSR (Standardized Root Mean Square Residual). In general, SRMR <= 0.08 and the result is 0.073. The confidence intervals d_ ULS and d_ G are obtained with a "normal" bootstrap approach, between the values of d_ ULS (squared Euclidean distance) and d_ G (geodesic distance) there is a correlation. Meanwhile, the Chi-Square is good because it is very small, namely 172.674, the NFI value is 0.929, which is close to 1, so this model is declared a fit model and accurate in predicting. Full in Table 6.

Test Hypothesis

Table 7. Hypothesis Result

	<i>Original sample</i>	<i>Sample mean</i>	<i>Standard deviation</i>	<i>T statistics</i>	<i>P values</i>
X1 <i>Employee Green Involvement -> Y1 Green Business Performance</i>	-0,044	-0,040	0,058	0,757	0,449
X2 <i>Green Motivation -> Y1 Green Business Performance</i>	0,688	0,687	0,070	9,849	0,008
X3 <i>Green Behavior -> Y1 Green Business Performance</i>	0,237	0,236	0,066	3,571	0,000

Table 7 shows that Employee Green Involvement has no effect on Green Business Performance which is indicated by the value of original sample -0.044 and the value of t-statistic 0.757 or a probability of 0.449. Meanwhile, green motivation and green behavior have positive and significant values for Green Business Performance seen from the original sample values of 0.688 and 0.237, t-statistic values of 9.849 and 3.571 or probabilities of 0.008 and 0.000.

Path Coefficients of P Values

Figure 1. Path Coefficients of P values

DISCUSSION

Employee Green Involvement Does Not Affect Green Business Performance

The first finding, a culture of informal and formal communication has not occurred in the company, this is based on questionnaire X1.3. Informal and formal communication channels have become an evergreen culture in our company (lowest mean), meaning that communication in the company has not yet become a green culture. This can have an impact on the decisions of the leadership, in this case managerial decisions are absolutely respected and carried out, this is because the top down of company policy lies with the leadership (Evina et al., 2024). Therefore, in making decisions, subordinates must also refer to superiors' decisions or in other words, must be based on the approval of the leadership (Amalia & Saputra, 2020). If there are suggestions from subordinates, then only as a

completeness with the approval of the leadership, not essentially changing the decision of the original leadership (Paladino et al., 2019).

When leadership decisions are important in employee green involvement in order to achieve good green business performance, efforts must be made to hold public forums and dialogues for employees to be involved in environmental activities enabling participation in decision-making related to solving environmental problems, which contributes on the development of voluntary environmental behavior (Masri & Jaaron, 2017). Companies should involve employees in making decisions related to solving environmental problems that arise to increase the willingness of employees to deal with the company's environment (Ragas et al., 2017).

The dominance of active employee participation in efforts to avoid environmental problems means that more and more employees are becoming aware of protecting the environment as their responsibility (Saputra & Renata, 2023), as well as improving the current environment (Arulrajah et al., 2016). This will have a positive impact in efforts to support a green environment on the development of work culture (Ahmed et al., 2021). Employee interest in protecting the environment also contributes to improving environmental management (Juliyando & Saputra, 2023).

Green Motivation Has a Positive and Significant Influence on Green Business Performance

The second finding, many motivated of employees by the green environment tasks they carry out, this corresponds to questionnaire X2.4. The environmental tasks that motivate me the most are recognized by the company (highest mean). This motivation is needed in the green environmental performance sector because if motivated of employees to comply, then they will be successful in implementing environmentally friendly practices, so that performance will increase (Hasan et al., 2019). Applying environmentally friendly motivation well will determine the success of an organization in creating performance management (Junsheng et al., 2020). Therefore, being motivated by environmentally friendly HR practices will produce a green environment (Li et al., 2020).

Recipients of environmentally friendly awards for employees will grow environmentally friendly motivation and performance (Mittal, 2016). As such, the research will explore the tendency of the workforce to participate in intrinsic or extrinsic environmentally friendly activities (Gilal et al., 2019).

Green Behavior Has a Positive and Significant Influence on Green Business Performance

The third finding, employees have fulfilled the tasks they are responsible for, this is in accordance with questionnaire item X3.2. The concept of being environmentally friendly is my responsibility at the office (highest mean). Green behavior is very much needed in companies, considering this as a behavior that protects and maintains the environment which is carried out because of awareness and a sense of responsibility for the preservation of the universe (Krsnik et al., 2022). Awareness and a sense of responsibility and concern must exist and be owned by every employee (Lau et al., 2023).

Improving the company's image occurs if employees care about the environment (Cai et al., 2020) because employees have direct contact with consumers. Involving employees in the process of formulating and planning environmental strategies will encourage employees' knowledge and ability to solve environmental problems (Chaudhary, 2019). When companies provide a green work environment, innovation will be created and always prioritize environmental values (Süßbauer & Schäfer, 2019).

CONCLUSION

This research produced three findings. The first finding, formal and informal communication has not become a culture in the company, second finding, many employees are motivated by the green environment tasks they carry out, third finding, employees have fulfilled the tasks they are responsible.

Suggestions for future research, developing vertical and horizontal communication in companies, so that performance is better, this is in accordance with the findings of the first research which were not significant. This development can be applied as a moderator or mediator variable.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The Kemendikbudristek Republic of Indonesia, LLDikti 5 Special Region of Yogyakarta, and Mercu Buana University Yogyakarta Indonesia in collaboration with industry in the Central Java region of Indonesia funded this research with contract number: 163/B. 03/H.01/II/2023, we thank you.

DECLARATION OF CONFLICTING INTEREST

There is no potential conflict of interest in this research between researchers, both data sources, writing and publication of this article.

REFERENCES

- Aggarwal, P., & Agarwala, T. (2021). Green Organizational Culture: An Exploration of Dimensions. *Global Business Review*, 22(5), 09721509211049890. <https://doi.org/10.1177/09721509211049890>
- Ahmed, M., Guo, Q., Qureshi, M. A., Raza, S. A., Khan, K. A., & Salam, J. (2021a). Do green HR practices enhance green motivation and proactive environmental management maturity in hotel industry? *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 94, 102852. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhm.2020.102852>
- Ahmed, M., Guo, Q., Qureshi, M. A., Raza, S. A., Khan, K. A., & Salam, J. (2021b). Do green HR practices enhance green motivation and proactive environmental management maturity in hotel industry? *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 94, 102852. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhm.2020.102852>
- Amalia, L., & Saputra, A. R. P. (2020). Pengaruh Intellectual Capital Terhadap Kinerja Keuangan Perusahaan Subsektor Advertising, Printing, Dan Media. *Jurnal Ilmiah Mahasiswa Ekonomi Manajemen*, 5(1), Article 1. <https://doi.org/10.24815/jimen.v5i1.14365>
- Anokye M, A. (2020). Sample Size Determination in Survey Research. *Journal of Scientific Research & Reports*, 26(5), 90–97. <https://doi.org/10.9734/JSRR/2020/v26i530263>
- Arulrajah, A. A., Opatha, H. H. D. N. P., & Nawaratne, N. N. J. (2016). Green human resource management practices: A review. *Sri Lankan Journal of Human Resource Management*, 5(1), 1. <https://doi.org/10.4038/sljhrm.v5i1.5624>
- Bentler, P. M., & Bonett, D. G. (1980). Significance tests and goodness of fit in the analysis of covariance structures. *Psychological Bulletin*, 88(3), 588–606. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0033-2909.88.3.588>
- Boiral, O., & Paillé, P. (2012). Organizational Citizenship Behaviour for the Environment: Measurement and Validation. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 109(4), 431–445. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-011-1138-9>
- Cai, W., Yang, C., Bossink, B. A. G., & Fu, J. (2020). Linking Leaders' Voluntary Workplace Green Behavior and Team Green Innovation: The Mediation Role of Team Green Efficacy. *Sustainability*, 12(8), 3404. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12083404>
- Chaudhary, R. (2019). Green human resource management in Indian automobile industry. *Journal of Global Responsibility*, 10(2), 161–175. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JGR-12-2018-0084>
- Chin, W. W. (1998). Commentary: Issues and opinion on structural equation modeling. *MIS Quarterly*, vii–xvi.

- Dumont, J., Shen, J., & Deng, X. (2017). Effects of Green HRM Practices on Employee Workplace Green Behavior: The Role of Psychological Green Climate and Employee Green Values: Effect of green HRM on employee workplace green behavior. *Human Resource Management*, 56(4), 613–627. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hrm.21792>
- Dźwigoł, H., Kwilinski, A., Oleksii, L., & Pimonenko, T. (2023). Renewable Energy, Knowledge Spillover and Innovation: Capacity of Environmental Regulation. *Energies*, 16(3), 1117. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en16031117>
- Evina, E., Saputra, A. R. P., & Nuvriasari, A. (2024). Green Training, Green Recruitment, and Green Transformational Leadership on Employee Performance in Retail Store. *International Journal of Management, Knowledge and Learning*, 13. <https://doi.org/10.53615/2232-5697.13.13-27>
- Fawehinmi, O., Yusliza, M. Y., Wan Kasim, W. Z., Mohamad, Z., & Sofian Abdul Halim, M. A. (2020). Exploring the Interplay of Green Human Resource Management, Employee Green Behavior, and Personal Moral Norms. *SAGE Open*, 10(4), 215824402098229. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2158244020982292>
- Fornell, C., & Larcker, D. F. (1981). *Structural equation models with unobservable variables and measurement error: Algebra and statistics*.
- Gilal, F. G., Ashraf, Z., Gilal, N. G., Gilal, R. G., & Chaana, N. A. (2019). Promoting environmental performance through green human resource management practices in higher education institutions: A moderated mediation model. *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management*, csr.1835. <https://doi.org/10.1002/csr.1835>
- Hair, J. F., Henseler, J., Dijkstra, T. K., & Sarstedt, M. (2014). *Common beliefs and reality about partial least squares: Comments on Rönkkö and Evermann*.
- Hardani, Auliya, N. H., Andriani, H., Fardani, A. R., Utami, F. E., Sukmana, J. D., & Istiqomah, R. R. (2020). *Metode Penelitian Kualitatif & Kuantitatif* (Cetakan 1). CV. Pustaka Ilmu.
- Hasan, Md. M., Nekmahmud, Md., Yajuan, L., & Patwary, M. A. (2019). Green business value chain: A systematic review. *Sustainable Production and Consumption*, 20, 326–339. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spc.2019.08.003>
- Jerónimo, H. M., Henriques, P. L., Lacerda, T. C. de, da Silva, F. P., & Vieira, P. R. (2020). Going green and sustainable: The influence of green HR practices on the organizational rationale for sustainability. *Journal of Business Research*, 112, 413–421. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2019.11.036>
- Juliyando, D., & Saputra, A. R. P. (2023). The Effect of Green Transformational Leadership on Service Employees in Indonesia. *International Journal of Service Management and Sustainability*, 8(1), Article 1. <https://doi.org/10.24191/ijSMS.v8i1.21896>
- Junsheng, H., Masud, M. M., Akhtar, R., & Rana, Md. S. (2020). The Mediating Role of Employees' Green Motivation between Exploratory Factors and Green Behaviour in the Malaysian Food Industry. *Sustainability*, 12(2), 509. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12020509>
- Krsnik, S., Erjavec, K., & Klopčič, M. (2022). Impact of Citizens' Personal Values, Knowledge, Awareness, Informing, Advertising, and Truth of Environmental and Climate Challenges in Support of the Sustainable Development Goals. *Sustainability*, 14(12), 3–11. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14127333>
- Lau, Y., Talukdar, G., Widyasamratri, H., Wang, J., & El-Shaammari, M. (2023). *Utilization of Green Materials and Technology for Sustainable Construction in Malaysia*. 47–66. <https://doi.org/10.53623/tebt.v1i1.238>

- Li, W., Bhutto, T. A., Xuhui, W., Maitlo, Q., Zafar, A. U., & Ahmed Bhutto, N. (2020). Unlocking employees' green creativity: The effects of green transformational leadership, green intrinsic, and extrinsic motivation. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 255, 120229. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.120229>
- Li, Y., Dai, J., & Cui, L. (2020). The impact of digital technologies on economic and environmental performance in the context of industry 4.0: A moderated mediation model. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 229, 107777. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpe.2020.107777>
- Liu, Z., Mei, S., & Guo, Y. (2021). Green human resource management, green organization identity and organizational citizenship behavior for the environment: The moderating effect of environmental values. *Chinese Management Studies*, 15(2), 290–304. <https://doi.org/10.1108/CMS-10-2019-0366>
- Malmendier, U., & Wachter, J. (2021). Memory of Past Experiences and Economic Decisions. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4013583>
- Manolas, E. (2017). Linaria: The green port of the island of Skyros. *International Journal of Environmental Studies*, 1–3. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00207233.2017.1360602>
- Masri, H. A., & Jaaron, A. A. M. (2017). Assessing green human resources management practices in Palestinian manufacturing context: An empirical study. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 143, 474–489. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2016.12.087>
- Matthes, J., & Wonneberger, A. (2014). The Skeptical Green Consumer Revisited: Testing the Relationship Between Green Consumerism and Skepticism Toward Advertising. *Journal of Advertising*, 43(2), 115–127. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00913367.2013.834804>
- Mittal, S. (2016). Effects of transformational leadership on turnover intentions in IT SMEs. *International Journal of Manpower*, 37(8), 1322–1346. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJM-10-2014-0202>
- Muntari, B., Ho, T., Teo, P.-C., Rizal, A., & Hee, O. (2021). The Link Between Green Human Resource Management and Green Management Practices in Achieving Green Competitive Advantage: The Moderating Role of Stakeholder Pressure. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 11(8), 1392–1401. <https://doi.org/10.6007/IJARBS/v11-i8/10836>
- Nurhayati, M., Kusumawardani, N., Saputra, A. R. P., & Santosa, A. (2023). Competence, Innovative Work Behavior, and Work Engagement: A Comparison of Generation X and Millennials. *Jurnal Organisasi Dan Manajemen*, 19(2), Article 2. <https://doi.org/10.33830/jom.v19i2.4855.2023>
- Özgül, B., & Zehir, C. (2021). The Influence of Green-Transformational Leadership Style on Corporate Sustainability: A Systematic Literature Review and Propositions for Future Studies. *Istanbul Management Journal*, 90, 1–30. <https://doi.org/10.26650/imj.2020.90.0001>
- Paladino, J., Sanders, J., & Fromme, E. (2019). Driving Organizational Change in Serious Illness Communication: Successes and Challenges of Implementing the Serious Illness Care Program (Qi729). *Journal of Pain and Symptom Management*, 57(2), 471–472. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpainsymman.2018.12.238>
- Purba, S. D., & Tikurura, R. (2022). Effect Mediation of Green Behaviors on Green Employee Involvement in Improving Job Satisfaction in Pusat Sistem Informasi dan Teknologi Keuangan (PUSINTEK). *KINERJA*, 26(1), 151–166. <https://doi.org/10.24002/kinerja.v26i1.5566>
- Ragas, S. F. P., Tantay, F. M. A., Chua, L. J. C., & Sunio, C. M. C. (2017). Green lifestyle moderates GHRM's impact on job performance. *International Journal of Productivity and Performance Management*, 66(7), 857–872. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJPPM-04-2016-0076>
- Rahman, R. N., & Saputra, A. R. P. (2023). The influence of green shared vision, education and training, and green recruitment, on organizational citizenship behavior for environment in elementary schools in Indonesia. *Journal of Management and Business Education*, 6(3), Article 3. <https://doi.org/10.35564/jmbe.2023.0018>

- Renwick, D. W. S., Redman, T., & Maguire, S. (2013). Green Human Resource Management: A Review and Research Agenda*: Green Human Resource Management. *International Journal of Management Reviews*, 15(1), 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-2370.2011.00328.x>
- Roscoe, S., Subramanian, N., Charbel, J. C. J., & Chong, T. (2019). Green Human Resource Management and the Enablers of Green Organisational Culture: Enhancing A Firm’s Environmental Performance for Sustainable Development. *Business Strategy and The Environment*, pp. 1–13. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1002/bse.2277>. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 28(5), 737–749. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bse.2277>
- Saepuddin, A., & Saputra, A. R. P. (2023). Effect Of Leadership Training, Welfare, And Mental Health In The Work Environment On The Performance Of Employees In Bekasi Regency. *The American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research*, 6(3), 89–98. <https://doi.org/10.56805/ajhssr>
- Saputra, A. R. P., & Renata, G. R. (2023). Pengaruh Green Training, Green Recruitment And Selection Dan Green Empowerment Terhadap Green Performance Management Di Bengkel Sepeda Motor AHASS Bantul. *Trending: Jurnal Manajemen Dan Ekonomi*, 1(4), Article 4. <https://doi.org/10.30640/trending.v1i4.1689>
- Sarstedt, M., Ringle, C. M., & Hair, J. F. (2014). PLS-SEM: Looking back and moving forward. *Long Range Planning*, 47(3), 132–137.
- Soewarno, N., Tjahjadi, B., & Fithrianti, F. (2019). Green innovation strategy and green innovation: The roles of green organizational identity and environmental organizational legitimacy. *Management Decision*, 57(11), 3061–3078. <https://doi.org/10.1108/MD-05-2018-0563>
- Soltaninezhad, A., Sharifabadi, A., Ahmadabadi, H., & Jafarnejad, A. (2021). Developing a model for strategic agility in knowledge-based companies using a mixed methods approach. *Journal of Industrial Engineering and Management*, 14, 176. <https://doi.org/10.3926/jiem.3083>
- Sun, X., El Askary, A., Meo, M. S., Zafar, N., & Hussain, B. (2022). Green transformational leadership and environmental performance in small and medium enterprises. *Economic Research-Ekonomika Istraživanja*, 1–19. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1331677X.2021.2025127>
- Süßbauer, E., & Schäfer, M. (2019). Corporate strategies for greening the workplace: Findings from sustainability-oriented companies in Germany. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 226, 564–577. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2019.04.009>
- Unsworth, K. L., Davis, M. C., Russell, S. V., & Bretter, C. (2021). Employee green behaviour: How organizations can help the environment. *Current Opinion in Psychology*, 42, 1–6. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.copsyc.2020.12.006>
- Uwem, E. I., Oyedele, O. O., & Olubiyi, O. T. (2021). Workplace Green Behavior for Sustainable Competitive Advantage: In S. O. Atiku & T. Fapohunda (Eds.), *Advances in Human Resources Management and Organizational Development* (pp. 248–263). IGI Global. <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-7998-4522-5.ch014>
- Venkatasathish, R., & Dhanamjayulu, C. (2022). Reinforcement learning based energy management systems and hydrogen refuelling stations for fuel cell electric vehicles: An overview. *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, 47(64), 27646–27670. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2022.06.088>
- Wahidul Sheikh et al., W. S. ... TJPRC. (2019). Implementing Green Human Resource Management, Cost-Effective Strategies and Tools. *International Journal of Human Resource Management and Research*, 9(3), 117–130. <https://doi.org/10.24247/ijhrmrjun201915>
- Werts, C. E., Linn, R. L., & Jöreskog, K. G. (1974). Intraclass Reliability Estimates: Testing Structural Assumptions. *Educational and Psychological Measurement*, 34(1), 25–33. <https://doi.org/10.1177/001316447403400104>

- Yoestini, Batu, K. L., Kusumawardani, A., & Andriyansah. (2022). GREEN BUSINESS PERFORMANCE BASED CSR (Evidences from Large Scale Enterprises in Indonesia). *Journal of European Periodical Studies*, 19. <https://doi.org/10.21825/jeps.81966>
- Yuriev, A., Boiral, O., Francoeur, V., & Paillé, P. (2018). *Overcoming the barriers to pro-environmental behaviors in the workplace: A systematic review*. 182(*Journal of Cleaner Production*), 379–394. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2018.02.041>
- Zhang, B., Yang, L., Cheng, X., & Chen, F. (2021). How Does Employee Green Behavior Impact Employee Well-Being? An Empirical Analysis. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 18(4), 1669. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph18041669>
- Zhang, Q., Feng, T., Cheng, L., & He, Q. (2022). Institutional force and firm performance: Do employee green involvement and flexibility-oriented culture matter? *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management*, 29(4), 950–964. <https://doi.org/10.1002/csr.2247>